

Promising cultivars with resistance to gall midge (GM) in Kerala, India

N. Rema Bai, R. Devika, A. Regina, and C. A. Joseph, Rice Research Station, Moncompu, India

A severe GM outbreak in Kuttanad, Kerala, caused damage that exceeded 50% in many varieties during the 1990 wet season (Apr–May to Aug–Sep).

We evaluated 53 breeding lines from the Directorate of Rice Research, Hyderabad, for GM resistance under natural conditions. Checks were susceptible Jaya and resistant Mahaveera. Each entry was planted in 5- × 2-m plots laid out in randomized block design with three replications.

Damage ranged from 0 to 58%. Damage severity in Mahaveera was 40%. Pest infestation was scored at 40 d after transplanting using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES). Eleven entries were highly resistant (score 0 to

Reaction of rice cultivars to gall midge incidence in Kerala, India.

IET no.	Parentage	Incidence of gall midge		Grain yield (t/ha)
		Score (0–9 scale)	Silvershoot (%)	
10774	Sona/W1263	3	5.0	5.2
11515	IET5656/RP1579	0	0.0	6.4
12169	CB11/Ratna	3	1.4	4.9
12170	Ash/Kranti	0	0.0	4.5
12183	ARC5723/ARC6650/RP1579-38	3	2.6	5.6
12185	Swarnadhan/ARC6650	1	0.8	4.7
12186	IR50/Phalgun	0	0.0	7.1
12187	IR50/Phalgun	0	0.0	6.7
12188	IR50/Phalgun	0	0.0	3.8
12189	Ratna/ARC10654	3	1.0	6.8
12193	Ratna/IET6858	0	0.0	5.1
12795	Rajendra/ARC6650	5	13.4	5.0
12799	Phalgun/IR50	0	0.0	6.0
12800	Phalgun/IR36	3	1.0	7.8
12804	IET6858/ARC6172	0	0.0	4.8
12806	IR50/Phalgun	0	0.0	6.2
12808	Prasanna/IET5688	3	1.5	5.8
12809	Manasarovar/ET6187	5	7.3	3.4
12814	SYE75/IR28	0	0.0	4.6
	Suraksha	5	13.5	3.9
	Mahaveera	7	40.0	2.8
	Jaya	9	53.0	2.6
	LSD		12.6	

1), 6 resistant (score 3), 3 moderately resistant (score 3, and 3 1 susceptible

(score 7). Jaya showed a high incidence (score 9) (see table). □

Virulence of brown planthopper (BPH) in Raipur, India

D. J. Pophaly and D. K. Rana, Entomology Department, I.G.K.V.V., Raipur, Madhya Pradesh (MP), India

BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* is becoming a major rice pest in Chhattisgarh region in MP. To determine BPH virulence in the area, we evaluated BPH resistance in

Table 1. Resistance of selected donors to the BPH-population in Raipur, MP, India, 1989-90.^a

Donor	BPH gene	Damage		Honeydew in 24 h (mm ² /female)
		Score	Rating ^a	
Balamawee	<i>Bph 9</i>	4.1	MR	12.61
Swarnalata	<i>bph 6</i>	0.5	R	18.66
Rathu Heenati	<i>Bph 3</i>	5.0	MR	31.51
Mudgo	<i>Bph 1</i>	9.0	S	78.89
ASD7	<i>bph2</i>	9.0	S	132.37
PTB33	R check	1.6	R	6.80
TN1	S check	9.0	S	66.34
ARC10550	<i>bph5</i>	0.8	R	10.10
Babawee	<i>bph4</i>	7.7	S	19.20
TN1		9.0	S	32.37

^aR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, S = susceptible.

Table 2. Reaction of DRP^a Hyderabad, and Pattambi donors of resistance to the Raipur BPH population.

Donor	Plant damage		Donor	Plant damage	
	Score	Rating ^b		Score	Rating ^b
	<i>Hyderabad</i>			<i>Pattambi</i>	
Andrewsali	5.29	S	KAU8754	6.6	S
ARC 10660	2.28	R	KAU8755	8.5	S
ARC11321	2.32	R	KAU8756	7.22	S
ARC6632	3.84	MR	KAU8770	4.41	MR
ARC10654	3.17	MR	MO 5	2.11	R
ARC5981	1.77	R	Jyoti	0.68	R
ARC6172	1.16	R	Rashmi	2.08	R
Majila	2.65	R	Bharthi	6.17	S
ARC6601	1.74	R	KAU8772	4.40	MR
ARC5780 (b)	1.88	R	KAU25331	7.96	S
ARC6610	1.85	R	KAU25333	5.92	S
ARC5984	1.94	R	BR51	2.57	R
ARC6650	1.03	R	Pavizam	4.24	MR
ARC10550	1.01	R	Triveni	5.3	S
Velluthacheera	1.41	R	KAU1727	9.0	S
Manoharsali	1.35	R	PTB33 (R check)	0.92	R
Soinphul	1.97	R			
PTB33 (R check)	2.61	R			

^aDRR = Directorate Rice Research, Hyderabad. AP. ^bR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, S = susceptible.

donors from Hyderabad (Andhra Pradesh), Pattambi (Kerala), and IRRI, Philippines during 1989–90.

The standard seedling test showed Mudgo (*Bph 1*), ASD7 (*bph 2*), and Babawee (*bph 4*) to be highly susceptible; Rathu Heenati (*Bph 3*) and Balamawee (*Bph 9*), moderately

resistant; and Swarnalata (*bph 6*) and ARC10550 (*bph 5*), resistant (Table 1). BPH honeydew excretion test confirmed the results.

Hyderabad donors were also resistant in Raipur, indicating similar virulency patterns at both locations (Table 2). Of the 15 donors from Pattambi, 8 were

susceptible; 5, resistant; and 3, moderately resistant. Results indicated that the Pattambi BPH population is likely to be less virulent than that at Raipur or Hyderabad. □

Evaluating rice cultivars for yellow stem borer (YSB) resistance

S. Ramakrishnan and M. S. Venugopal, Horticultural Research Station, Tamil Nadu G.D. Naidu Agricultural University, Udhagamandalam 643001, Tamil Nadu, India

Forty-one rice cultivars were screened for field resistance to YSB during 1988 at the Rice Research Station, Tirur, India.

Seedlings (30-d-old) for each entry were spaced at 20 × 10 cm in three 4-m rows in a randomized block design with three replications. Susceptible check Jaya was planted in single rows between entries in each replication and in three rows between replications.

Deadheart was counted 15, 30, and 45 d after transplanting (DT) and whitehead at 10 d before harvest for 20 randomly selected hills for each entry. Infestation was scored using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES).

W1263 was resistant at 15 DT and moderately resistant at other times. TM8089, TM2011, and CO 43 were moderately susceptible at 15 and 30 DT. TKM9 was moderately susceptible at all times (see table). □

Field reaction^a of rice varieties to YSB under natural infestation, Tirur, India, 1988.

Accession	Parentage	Deadheart score ^b			Whitehead score 10 d before harvest
		15 DT	30 DT	45 DT	
TM8089	Selffrom TKM9	5	5	7	9
TM2011	C22/TKM6/TR50	5	5	7	9
TM4640	BAM3/IR50	5	7	7	9
TM4309	BAM3/IR50	5	7	7	7
TPS1	IR8/Kattaisamba	7	7	7	9
PMK1	CO 25/ADT31	7	7	7	9
IET7511	Ras/Barket	7	7	7	9
TKM9	TKM7/IR8	5	5	5	5
ADT37	BG280-2/PTB33	7	7	7	9
TM6012	C22/BJ1	7	7	7	3
TM5656	IR50/TKM9	7	7	7	9
TM5118	BAM3/IR50	7	7	7	9
TM10232	TKM6/IET1444	7	7	7	9
TM1086	Ponni/ME80	5	7	7	7
TM5670	IR50/TKM9	7	7	7	9
TM4937	BAM3/IR50	7	7	7	9
TM4955	BAM3/IR50	7	7	7	9
TM4865	AC76/TKM8	7	7	7	9
TM8601	TKM9/ADT9/CR141/IR26	7	7	7	9
TM8381	IR262/CR1106-190	7	7	7	7
TM8602	CO 31/22	7	7	7	9
TM4300	IR262/Bhavani	7	7	7	9
TMA1087	Ponni/CH1039	7	7	7	7
TNAU891434	IET6262/TBAY1756	5	7	7	9
TNAU840337	TKM9/White Ponni	5	7	7	9
TNAU6790/2	BAM3/TN1	7	7	7	9
TNAU6540/2	GMR2/BAM3	7	7	7	7
TNAU843062	IET4141/CO43	5	7	7	9
PM1381	IR13564-149-3/ASD4	7	7	7	7
PM1340	IR13564/ASD4	7	7	7	7
MW10	MTU15/Yaikyakunantoku	7	7	7	9
AS26556	IET5233/IR2153-26-3-5-2	5	7	7	9
ACM38	ASD4/TKM6	9	7	9	9
CO 11	GEB24/ <i>O. perennis</i>	7	7	7	7
IR20	IR262/CR106-190	7	7	7	5
ADT38	IR1529/IR4432/IR7963	5	7	7	9
CO 43	Daral/IR20	5	5	7	9
ADT39	IR8/IR20	7	7	7	9
White Ponni	Tg 65/ME80	7	7	7	7
W1263	MTU15/Eswarakora	1	3	3	3
Jaya	TN1/T14	9	9	9	9

^aDeadheart and whitehead scores by SES. ^bDT = days after transplanting.

Field reaction of rice breeding lines to brown planthopper (BPH) in Pondicherry, India

B. Rajendran, Krishi Vigyan Kendra, Pondicherry 605009, India

BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) is an important pest in Pondicherry region, especially in sornavari season (May to Aug/Sep). During 1988 and 1989 wet seasons (Jun-Sep) 143 entries of advanced rice breeding lines (including local susceptible and resistant checks) From the Directorate of Rice Research, Hyderabad, were screened in the field against BPH.

Field reaction of selected breeding lines to BPH in Pondicherry, India, 1988 and 1989 wet seasons.

Designation	Cross	BPH damage score ^a			Reaction to other pests ^b
		1988	1989	Mean	
BPT2217	BPT3291/ARC6650	3	1	2	—
BPT4363	BPT3291/Velluthacheera	3	1	2	—
BPT4365	BPT3291/Velluthacheera	3	1	2	—
RP1579-13-11-12	Phalguna/ARC6650	5	3	4	RTV-P
RP1746-1723-8	RPA5824/RP79-9//Rasi///PTB21	3	3	3	LF-S
RP2332-16-3	Ratna/ARC10654	3	3	3	LF-S
RP2332-18-15	Ratna/ARC10654	3	3	3	LF-S
RP2332-19-9-6	Ratna/ARC10654	3	3	3	—
RP2362-227-22	Nagarjuna/ARC5989	3	3	3	—
RP2542-1657-194	Swarnadhan/RP1579-37	3	3	3	—
RP2.543-1444-46	Rasi/RP1579-38	3	3	3	—
RP2.543-1464-152	Rasi/RP1579-38	3	3	3	—
RP2547-985-100	RP2205/RP1579-38	5	5	5	—
RP2547-1059-118	RP2205/RP1579-38	5	5	5	—
IR50 (local susceptible check)	—	9	9	9	—
ADT36 (local check)	—	3	3	3	—
PY3 (local resistant check)	—	1	3	2	LF-S
TN1 (standard susceptible check)	—	9	9	9	—

^aBy the *Standard evaluation system for rice*. ^bRTV-P = rice tungro virus present, LF-S = leafroller susceptible.